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Study Information

1. Title (required)

Inconsistencies of within-country prevalence rates of (cyber)bullying and (cyber)victimization in large scale cross-national datasets: Which role do different bullying definitions play?

2. Authors (required)

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3. Description (optional)

Previous research documented substantial within-country discrepancies in prevalence rates of (cyber)victimization when comparing the results of different cross national large-scale surveys (Smith et al., 2016; Smith & López-Castro, 2017). One explanation for the documented within-country discrepancies are different measurement approaches. The main goal of the present study is to examine whether the type of bullying definition sheds light on the observed within-country discrepancies.

This study will analyze data gathered from overlapping countries in two large scale datasets: EUKO (EU Kids Online) and HBSC (Health Behavior in School-aged Children). In both datasets bullying, victimization, cyberbullying, and cybervictimization were assessed through global items that were preceded by a bullying definition. However, these two studies differed regarding the type of bullying definition. While the EUKO study included several concrete behavioral examples and avoided the term “bullying”, the HBSC study used the classic definition comprising of hostile intent, repetition, and power-imbalance (Solberg & Olweus, 2003) and the term “bullying”. Furthermore, the two definitions covered different time spans. While the EUKO study covered a longer time span (e.g., the last year), the HBSC study covered a shorter time span (e.g., the past couple of months). Therefore, because of these different definitions, the EUKO study covers a broader phenomenon compared to the HBSC study.

Thus, by systematically comparing the within-country prevalence rates of the EUKO and HBSC study, it is possible to elucidate the effect of the definition when controlling for as many variables as possible that systematically varied between studies.

4. Hypotheses (required)

- 4.1. We hypothesize that there is a difference in prevalence rates of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization between the EUKO and the HBSC study when looking at the whole sample (all 19 countries together). More specifically, we hypothesize that the EUKO study will produce systematically higher prevalence rates than the HBSC study, because the definition provided in the EUKO study covers a broader range of behaviors compared to the more focused bullying definition provided in the HBSC study (Hypothesis 1, effect of definition).
- 4.2. We hypothesize that the differences of prevalence rates of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization between the EUKO and the HBSC study will be the same in all 19 countries, because there is no theoretical or evidence-based reason to assume that the provision of different definitions work differently in different countries (Hypothesis 2, effect of country).
- 4.3. To rule out the possibility that differences in prevalence rates between EUKO and HBSC are due to sample characteristics, we will investigate the effects of age and gender on prevalence rates of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization. We expect that the influence of age and gender on prevalence rates will be the same between EUKO and HBSC. More specifically, we expect that boys and younger adolescents will report higher prevalence rates compared to girls and older adolescents in both EUKO and HBSC in all countries, and that the systematic differences in prevalence rates of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization between EUKO and HBSC will persist (Hypothesis 3, effect of sample characteristics).
- 4.4. To rule out the possibility that differences in prevalence rates between EUKO and HBSC are due to study type characteristics, we will investigate the effects of study design features, e.g., the average age of the participants, the proportion of girls, the response rates, and the sampling method. Controlling for these study design features which vary between EUKO and HBSC in different countries, we expect that the systematic differences in prevalence rates of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization between EUKO and HBSC will persist (Hypothesis 4, effect of study design).
- 4.5. In both the EUKO and the HBSC study, it is possible to create prevalence rates of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization based on a strict and lenient cut-off score. To provide a robustness test, all analyses will be performed with a lenient and a strict cut-off score. We expect that the results formulated in hypothesis 1 to 4 will be found for both the lenient and the strict cut-off scores (Hypothesis 5, effect of categorization).

Design Plan

5. Study type (required)
 - 5.1. Observational Study – a cross-sectional multi-national survey study.
6. Blinding (required)
 - 6.1. No blinding is involved in this study.
7. Is there any additional blinding in this study?
 - 7.1. No.
8. Study design (required)
 - 8.1. Secondary data study. We will have a cross-sectional study using data from cross-sectional studies that were conducted in 19 countries, joint in the same dataset .
9. Randomization (optional)
 - 9.1. Non applicable.

Sampling Plan

10. Existing data (required)
 - 10.1. Registration prior to analysis of the data: As of the date of submission, the data exist and we have accessed the EUKO 2020 and HBSC 2017-18 datasets, though no analysis has been conducted related to the research plan (including calculation of summary statistics).
11. Explanation of existing data (optional)
 - 11.1. The EUKO 2020 data has not been publicly accessible yet. But we have reached out to the expert for the EUKO data who also takes care of its archiving and received the download link for the raw data. The HBSC 2017-18 datasets is publicly accessible. We filled out the request form and were able to download it.
 - 11.2. Different from previous research using correlation on the country level between these two studies, we will recode rating scales in a logical way (according to coding strategies provided in section 18.1) to make prevalence rates more comparable.
12. Data collection procedures (required)
 - 12.1. This study used the secondary data which is selected based on several factors:

- 12.1.1. EUKO 2020 and HBSC 17/18 were conducted around the same time period. EUKO 2020 was carried out from autumn 2017 to summer 2019, with the exception of Ireland, which occurred between December 2019 and October 2020. In the EUKO study, 20 countries participated. HBSC 17/18 was conducted from June 2017 to February 2019. In the HBSC study, 45 countries participated.
- 12.1.2. There are 19 countries that overlap between these two studies - Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Malta, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland.
- 12.1.3. EUKO focused on children aged 9-17 years old, and the subjects of HBSC are pupils aged 11, 13, and 15.
- 12.2. Data collection procedures in EUKO 2020:

According to Smahel and colleagues (2020), two sampling methods were utilized: sampling via households and via schools. Each participating country selected the method depending on available resources and country and cultural context. Variants of household sampling included random walk, quota sampling and random recruitment/selection of households from a specific register. Overlapping countries that used household sampling were Croatia, Estonia, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Russia, Slovakia, and Ireland (10 countries). The sampling and data collection in France was carried by using the online panel of the agency OpinionWay. For sampling via schools, students enrolled in regular, vocational, general, and academic studies were included. Those who were enrolled in either special schools or special classes for students with learning disorders or severe physical disabilities were not included. Overlapping countries that used school sampling were the Czech Republic, Belgium (Flanders), Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Spain, and Switzerland (9 countries). Two of the overlapping countries, Belgium (Flanders) and Russia, used specific sampling that also precluded the weighting options and also excluded younger children from the survey (age 9–11). The data collection by trained administrators was conducted by professional agencies, affiliated institute, or by national teams. Most countries using the household sampling method also used some form of incentives (except for Germany, Lithuania, and Russia). The individual nature of the incentive ranged from a symbolic gift serving as a thank you to monetary compensation for time provided. The data were collected via three base methods: CASI/CAWI (computer-assisted self-interviewing/computer-assisted web interviewing), CAPI (computer-assisted personal interviewing), and PAPI (paper-assisted personal interviewing).
- 12.3. Data collection procedures in HBSC 2017/18:

According to HBSC2017/18 open access data file documentation, most students were selected through a random selection of classes within

targeted school years/grades. In most cases only one class per grade was selected from one school, but on occasion there were more than one (e.g., if class sizes were small). Sampling was set out using: 1) simple random sampling of school classes using a computerized random sampling procedure, 2) systematic sampling of every n-th class from the list using a random starting point.

13. Sample size (required)
 - 13.1. EUKO: About 1,000 students in each country. Because this study uses data from 19 overlapping countries with HBSC, the sample size is around 19,000 students.
 - 13.2. HBSC: approximately 1500 students per age group (11, 13, and 15) in each country or region (totaling around 4500). This study will use data from 19 overlapping countries with EUKO. Therefore, the sample size is approximately 85,500 students.

Variables

14. Manipulated variables (optional)
 - 14.1. Describe all variables you plan to manipulate and the levels or treatment arms of each variable. This is not applicable to the current observational study.
15. Measured variables (required)
 - 15.1. We will compare participants from EUKO and HBSC, regarding the outcome variables reporting bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization. The four outcome variables will be the answers to the global item of the self-reported prevalence rates of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying, and cybervictimization.
 - 15.1.1. In EUKO, concrete examples of behaviors were initially offered to children as the definition of bullying - 'Sometimes children or teenagers say or do hurtful or nasty things to someone, and this can often be quite a few times on different days over a period of time, for example. This can include: teasing someone in a way this person does not like; hitting, kicking or pushing someone around; leaving someone out of things. When people are hurtful or nasty to someone in this way, it can happen: face to face (in person); by mobile phones (texts, calls, video clips); on the internet (e-mail, instant messaging, social networking, chatrooms)' (Smahel et al., 2020).
Then students were asked about their own concrete behaviors '*In the past year, have you ever treated someone else in a hurtful or nasty way?*' and about their own concrete experiences '*In the past year, has anyone ever treated you in such a hurtful or nasty way?*' Those who answered 'yes' to these two questions were further asked 'How often did this happen in any of the following ways?' and presented with a list of different

behavioral options. For the present study, we will use two behavioral options, namely 'In person face to face' to capture bullying and victimization and 'Via a mobile phone or internet, computer, tablet, etc' to capture cyberbullying and cybervictimization. These behaviors were answered on a rating scale ranging between 1-7, namely 1 'never', 2 'a few times', 3 'at least every month', 4 'at least every week', 5 'daily or almost daily', 6 'I don't know', 7 'prefer not to say'.

- 15.1.2. According to HBSC2017/18 open access data file documentation, the definition of bullying was provided: 'We say a person is being bullied when another person or a group of people, repeatedly say or do unwanted nasty and unpleasant things to him or her. It also is bullying when a person is teased in a way he or she does not like or when he or she is left out of things on purpose. The person that bullies has more power than the person being bullied and wants to cause harm to him or her. It is not bullying when two people of about the same strength or power argue or fight.'
- Then, bullying, victimization, cyberbullying, and cybervictimization were measured by asking participants 'How often have you taken part in bullying another person(s) at school in the past couple of months', 'How often have you been bullied at school in the past couple of months', 'In the past couple of month how often have you taken part in cyberbullying (e.g., sent mean instant messages, email or text messages; wall postings; created a website making fun of someone; posted unflattering or inappropriate pictures online without permission or shared them with others)', and 'In the past couple of month how often have you been cyberbullied (e.g., someone sent mean instant messages, email or text messages about you; wall postings; created a website making fun of you; posted unflattering or inappropriate pictures of you online without permission or shared them with others). The items were answered on a rating scale of 1-5, 1 'never', 2 'once or twice', 3 '2-3 times per months', 4 'once a week', 5 'several times a week'.

16. Indices (optional)

- 16.1. Since both EUKO and HBSC surveys measure outcome variables using one single item, scale analyses will not be performed.

Analysis Plan

17. Statistical models (required)

- 17.1. To test hypothesis 1, multi-level analyses will be used. Study type (EUKO and HBSC) is a within-country level predictor, and countries are the between-level units.
- 17.2. To test hypothesis 2, a random slope will be specified for study type to test whether there is variance in prevalences between countries. Bayesian multilevel modeling with Bayes factors will be applied to see whether the null hypothesis is plausible.
- 17.3. To test hypothesis 3, gender and age are added as within-country level variables. The interaction gender x EUKO vs HBSC and age x EUKO vs. HBSC will be tested applying Bayesian multilevel modeling with Bayes factors to see whether the null hypothesis is plausible.
- 17.4. To test hypothesis 4, study type characteristics (e.g., the average age of the participants, the proportion of girls, response rates, type of sampling strategy) are added as within-country level variables. Controlling for these study type characteristics, we still expect systematically different prevalence rates of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization across EUKO and HBSC data (Hypothesis 4, effect of study design).
- 17.5. To test hypothesis 5 (e.g., whether the cut-off score of the items changes the results), all the analyses will be repeated with the lenient cut-off score. Because we hypothesize that the overall pattern of results is not altered by the cut-off scores, the same results are expected as in the multi-level models 1, 2 and 3.

Multilevel modeling (Hox et al., 2018) will be conducted in R (R Core Team, 2024) using Bayesian estimation to deal with the small sample size at the country level (Hox & McNeish, 2020). Weakly informative prior distributions will be specified for the model parameters in line with to the default settings of the R package rstanarm (Goodruck et al., 2024). Null hypothesis Bayesian testing (NHBT) using Bayes factors will be conducted to test the hypotheses of the present study (Tendeiro & Kiers, 2019). Note that the Bayes factor provides the relative evidence of the data for the null hypothesis compared to the alternative hypothesis (Schmalz et al., 2023), which is required for testing hypotheses 2 and 3.

18. Transformations (optional)

- 18.1. Due to differences in the rating scales of bullying, victimization, cyberbullying, and cybervictimization between EUKO and HBSC, we will use two cut-off scores - a lenient and a strict cutoff-score (see Table below). In both EUKO and HBSC, the lenient cut-off score covers dummy-coded response options in which “never” describes the students not involved in bullying, victimization, cyberbullying and cybervictimization and all other answer options describe the students that were involved. For the strict-cut-off score, we will compare involved students who have experienced bullying, victimization, cyberbullying, and cybervictimization “at least every week’ in EUKO and ‘once a week’ in HBSC and ‘daily or almost daily’ in EUKO and ‘several times a week’ in HBSC, while non-involved students comprise the ones that answered either never, a few times and at least every month in EUKO and never, once or twice and 2-3 times per month in HBSC.

		Not involved (0)	Involved (1)
Lenient cutoff	EUKO	1. never	2. a few times 3. at least every month 4. at least every week 5. daily or almost daily 6. I don't know, 7. prefer not to say.
	HBSC	1. never	2. once or twice 3. 2-3times per month 4. once a week 5. several times a week
Strict cutoff	EUKO	1. never 2. a few times 3. at least every month	4. at least every week 5. daily or almost daily
	HBSC	1. never 2. once or twice 3. 2-3times per month	4. once a week 5. several times a week

19. Data exclusion (optional)

19.1. This section does not apply.

20. Missing data (optional)

20.1. If a subject does not provide data on at least one of the four outcome variables, that subject will not be included in the analysis.

Other

21. Other (Optional)

21.1. References

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